

"Effect of Gd³⁺ Substitution on the Structural, Magnetic, and Dielectric Behaviour of Ni_{0.7}Co_{0.3}Fe₂O₄ Ferrites"

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Abstract:

This study investigates the structural, magnetic, dielectric, and morphological properties of Ni_{0.7}Co_{0.3}Gd_xFe_{2-x}O₄ (where x = 0.00 and 0.015) ferrite nanoparticles synthesized via a wet chemical method. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis reveals that Gd³⁺ doping leads to a slight increase in lattice constant from 8.3502 Å to 8.3545 Å, indicating lattice expansion due to the substitution of larger Gd³⁺ ions for Fe³⁺. The crystallite size decreases from 35.93 nm (pure Ni-Co ferrite) to 23.39 nm for the Gd-doped sample, which is attributed to lattice distortions that hinder crystal growth. Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) images show that the particles exhibit a spherical morphology and significant agglomeration, a typical feature of ferrite nanoparticles. Magnetic measurements performed using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) indicate an increase in saturation magnetization (from 30.67 emu/g to 35.41 emu/g) and remanent magnetization (from 15.87 emu/g to 17.81 emu/g) with Gd doping. Coercivity decreases slightly, suggesting enhanced domain wall mobility. Dielectric studies show an increase in dielectric constant, particularly at lower frequencies, due to enhanced polarization mechanisms facilitated by Gd³⁺ substitution. These findings demonstrate that Gd doping improves the multifunctional properties of Ni-Co ferrites, making them suitable for applications in high-frequency electronic devices, magnetic sensors.

Key words: Ni-Co ferrites, Gd doping, Magnetic properties, Dielectric properties.

1. Introduction:

Nickel-Cobalt ferrites (Ni-Co ferrites) are a class of magnetic materials with exceptional properties, including high magnetic permeability, low eddy current losses, and good thermal stability, making them suitable for a wide range of applications in electronics, communication systems, and energy storage devices. The incorporation of rare-earth ions such as gadolinium (Gd^{3+}) into these ferrites has garnered significant attention in recent years due to the enhanced magnetic properties and potential improvements in their electrical and magnetic behaviours. Gd^{3+} -doped nickel-cobalt ferrites, in particular, show promise for applications in high-frequency devices, microwave absorption, biomedical fields, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) due to their tunable magnetic characteristics.[1 2]

Recent research has focused on optimizing the doping levels of Gd^{3+} in Ni-Co ferrites to enhance their magnetic properties, particularly in high-frequency applications. The doping of Gd^{3+} is known to improve the magnetic resonance properties and increase the coercivity and magnetization, making these materials suitable for use in microwave absorption and electromagnetic shielding. Furthermore, the incorporation of Gd^{3+} into ferrites has been explored for biomedical applications, where they can be used in magnetic hyperthermia for cancer treatment, as well as in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) due to their strong magnetic resonance properties. Additionally, Gd^{3+} -doped ferrites are being investigated for use in energy storage devices, where their enhanced electrochemical behavior can improve the performance of super capacitors and batteries.[3 4]

The preparation of Gd^{3+} -doped Ni-Co ferrites requires careful control over the composition and synthesis conditions to achieve desired properties. Among various methods, the citrate gel auto-combustion technique has emerged as a highly effective approach for synthesizing high-quality ferrite materials with controlled particle size, enhanced crystallinity, and superior magnetic properties. This method is particularly attractive for its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and ability to produce ferrite powders with high homogeneity at relatively low temperatures. This approach not only accelerates the synthesis process but also ensures better control over the stoichiometry and microstructure of the ferrite material. [5 6]

This study investigates the structural, optical, and magnetic properties of Gd^{3+} -doped Nickel-Cobalt (Ni-Co) ferrites. The incorporation of Gd^{3+} ions into the ferrite structure is examined to understand its effect on the material's overall characteristics.

2. Materials and Methods:

Gd-doped Ni-Co ferrites were synthesized using the sol-gel auto-combustion method. Analytical-grade metal nitrates ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{Gd}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were dissolved in deionized water to prepare solution. These were mixed with citric acid as a chelating agent in a 1:3 molar ratio, and the resulting mixture was stirred for 3 hours and ammonia was added to maintain the pH at 7. The solution was then heated at 80°C , after 8-9 hours, the solution turned into a viscous brown gel, which was then heated to initiate auto-combustion, transforming it into ash. The ash was ground into fine powder, which was sintered at 500°C for 4 hours to improve crystallinity and magnetic properties. Synthesis flowchart as shown in Fig.1.[7]

Fig. 1 Synthesis flowchart of Gd^{3+} doped Ni – Co Ferrites.

3. Characterization Techniques:

The structural analysis of the synthesized samples was performed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) with an Ultima IV system from Rigaku Corporation (Japan). This technique provided insights into the crystallographic structure and phase composition of the samples. UV-Visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy was employed to assess the optical properties of the materials, utilizing a Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrometer with a UMA attachment for enhanced analysis of absorption and transmission spectra. Magnetic properties were investigated through vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM) using a PPMS-VSM measurement system, which enabled the evaluation of key magnetic parameters such as saturation magnetization and coercivity. For the dielectric characterization, a PSM1700 LCR meter was utilized to measure the impedance and capacitance of the samples across a range of frequencies, providing critical information on their dielectric behavior and electrical conductivity.

4. Results and Discussions:

4.1 X – Ray Diffraction Studies:

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of both pure and Gd-doped Ni-Co ferrites, represented by $\text{Ni}_{0.7}\text{Co}_{0.3}\text{Gd}_x\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=0.00$ and 0.015), confirmed the retention of the spinel structure in both samples as shown in Fig(2). The diffraction patterns displayed typical peaks without any additional phases, indicating successful incorporation of the doping ions into the ferrite lattice.

Scherrer-Debye equation was used to calculate the average crystallite size (D) of all samples

$$D = \frac{0.91*\lambda}{\beta\cos\theta} \quad (1)$$

The lattice constant 'a' is calculated using Bragg's equation (2) from the high-intensity peak (311).

$$a = d\sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2} \quad (2)$$

From the table.1, the lattice constant increased slightly from 8.3502 Å for the pure Ni-Co ferrite to 8.3545 Å for the Gd-doped sample. This increase suggests that the larger Gd^{3+} ions substituted for Fe^{3+} and caused a slight expansion of lattice. The crystallite size decreased from 35.93 nm for the pure Ni-Co ferrite to 23.39 nm for the Gd-doped sample. This reduction is likely due to lattice distortions caused by the larger Gd ions, hindering crystal growth and leading to smaller crystallites. Despite these changes, the spinel structure was preserved in both the pure and Gd-doped samples, with diffraction peaks corresponding to the (311), (220), (400), and (422) planes, indicating that Gd doping does not cause a phase transition but instead leads to structural modifications.[8 9]

Table.1 Calculated XRD parameters of Gd^{3+} doped Ni – Co Ferrites.

x	a (\AA)	D (nm)
0.00	8.3502	35.93
0.015	8.3545	23.39

Fig. 2. X- Ray Diffraction patterns of Gd^{3+} doped Ni – Co Ferrites.

4.2 FE-SEM Studies:

Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) was employed to examine the surface morphology of $Ni_{0.7}Co_{0.3}Gd_xFe_{2-x}O_4$ ($x = 0.00$ and 0.015) ferrite samples. The micrographs indicate that the particles possess a generally spherical morphology and exhibit significant agglomeration, which is a common characteristic of ferrite nano particles synthesized by wet chemical or sol-gel routes. This agglomeration can be attributed to the magnetic interactions between particles and the high surface energy typical of nanoscale materials.[10]

Fig. 3 FE-SEM micrographs of Gd^{3+} doped Ni – Co Ferrites.

4.3 Magnetic Studies:

Magnetic characteristics of Gd^{3+} doped nickel cobalt ferrites, measurements were carried out using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) attached to a Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS). This setup enabled high-precision evaluation of magnetization as a function of applied magnetic field." Gd doping ($x = 0.015$) increased the saturation magnetization (M_S) from 30.67 emu/g (pure Ni-Co ferrite) to 35.41 emu/g, due to the larger magnetic moment of Gd^{3+} ions compared to Fe^{3+} . Remanent magnetization (M_r) also increased, from 15.87 emu/g to 17.81 emu/g, suggesting enhanced magnetic domain alignment[11 12]. Coercivity (H_c) slightly decreased from 1702.54 Oe to 1681.48 Oe, likely due to lattice distortions from the larger Gd^{3+} ions, which facilitate easier domain switching.

Fig. 4 M – H loops of Gd^{3+} doped Ni – Co Ferrites.

4.4 Dielectric Studies:

Dielectric properties of the $\text{Ni}_{0.7}\text{Co}_{0.3}\text{Gd}_x\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{O}_4$ system (for $x = 0.00$ and 0.015) were examined over a frequency range of 10 Hz to 1 MHz at room temperature. It was noted that the dielectric constant increases with Gd doping, particularly at frequencies of 100 Hz and 1000 Hz.

The rise in dielectric constant with Gd^{3+} substitution can be explained by the enhancement of interfacial polarization, also known as Maxwell-Wagner polarization, which is prominent at lower frequencies. When Gd^{3+} ions are introduced into the ferrite lattice in place of Fe^{3+} ions, they modify the distribution of cations between the tetrahedral (A) and octahedral (B) sites, affecting the overall electronic structure. Gd^{3+} doping can lead to increased hopping of charge carriers, particularly between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} at the B-sites, which enhances polarization under an applied electric field. This improved polarization mechanism results in a higher dielectric constant at low frequencies [13 14]. These materials are therefore promising for applications in high-frequency electronic devices, magnetic sensors, EMI suppression components, and energy storage systems.

Fig. 5 Dielectric constant of Gd^{3+} doped Ni – Co Ferrites.

5. Conclusions:

The structural, morphological, magnetic, and dielectric properties of $\text{Ni}_{0.7}\text{Co}_{0.3}\text{Gd}_x\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.00$ and 0.015) ferrites were thoroughly examined. X-ray diffraction analysis revealed a slight increase in lattice constant from 8.3502 \AA to 8.3545 \AA with Gd^{3+} doping, attributed to the substitution of larger Gd^{3+} ions for Fe^{3+} , leading to minor lattice expansion. The crystallite size decreased from 35.93 nm to 23.39 nm due to lattice distortion, which restricted crystal growth. Despite these changes, the cubic spinel structure was maintained in both compositions. FE-SEM images showed that the particles were mostly spherical and agglomerated, typical for nanoscale ferrites, due to strong magnetic interactions and high surface energy. Magnetic measurements demonstrated an increase in saturation magnetization (from 30.67 to 35.41 emu/g) and remanence (from 15.87 to 17.81 emu/g) with Gd doping, owing to the higher magnetic moment of Gd^{3+} ions. A slight reduction in coercivity indicated easier domain wall movement. Dielectric analysis showed an increase in dielectric constant at low frequencies due to enhanced interfacial polarization and improved electron hopping between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions. Overall, Gd doping effectively improves the multifunctional properties of Ni-Co ferrites, making them suitable candidates for use in magnetic sensors, high-frequency devices, EMI suppression, and energy storage applications.

6. References:

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